

Measurement of Radium Content and Radon Exhalation Rates from Some Soil Samples of Sri Ksetra Ancient City (Pyay Township)

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Abstract

The earth is radioactive since its creation. The radioactive elements such as uranium, radium and radon are present in soil, air and water. The inhalation and ingestion of these radionuclides, above the permissible level, becomes a health hazard. In the present work, soil samples were collected from five different areas at Sri Ksetra Ancient City of Pyay Township and assessed for radon and radium content using LR-115 Solid State Nuclear Track Detector. The 'CAN' technique has employed for measuring the radon concentration, radium content, exhalation rates in terms of area and mass were calculated for these samples. Soil samples from the surface of the ground, under the depths of 1 ft and 2 ft were taken for each area. For the surface of the ground, radium concentration in soil samples has been found to vary from 0.81 Bq kg^{-1} to 2.59 Bq kg^{-1} . The radon exhalation rate in terms of area varies from $105.88 \text{ mbq m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $340.58 \text{ mbq m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ while radon exhalation rate in terms of mass varies from $2.66 \text{ mbq kg}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $8.56 \text{ mbq kg}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$. The values except from HMA-59 were found to be within the safe limit as recommended by ICRP and these areas are safe from the health hazard site of view as far as the radon is concerned.

Keywords: Radium concentration, exhalation rate, LR-115 Solid State Nuclear Track Detector, Soil

Introduction

Radiation plays an important role in our daily life as the world is naturally radioactive. People are exposed to ionizing radiation from naturally occurring radionuclides that are present in the soil. The rate at which radon escapes from soil into the surrounding air is known as radon exhalation rate of the soil. Radionuclides in soils, belonging to ^{232}Th and ^{238}U series as well as radioisotope of potassium (^{40}K) are the major contributors of outdoor terrestrial natural radiation. Radon has been found to be ubiquitous indoor radioactive air pollutant to which man is exposed. The most important radio-nuclides ^{226}Ra and ^{222}Rn are the decay products of the dominant isotope of ^{238}U . Radon isotopes are the daughter product of radium. Radon is a significant contaminant that affects indoor air quality worldwide. Radon gas from natural sources can accumulate in buildings.

Radon is a colorless, odorless, tasteless and naturally occurring radioactive gas. Radon varies in different quantities in different materials and place to place because radon is chemically unreactive with several materials, it is freely moving between particles of materials (like soil, rock and sand) to the soil surface. Radon being an inert gas and having sufficient half life can diffuse through the soil and enter the atmosphere. The radon produced in the soil migrates through the mechanism of emanation, diffusion and convection through pore spaces in solid, fractures in rocks and along with weak zones such as shear, faults thrust etc. The amount of radon that escapes from the earth depends mainly on the amount of ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th , in the ground along with other factors like the type of soil cover porosity etc.

The alpha particles emitted from ^{222}Rn and two of its daughter element viz. ^{214}Po and ^{218}Po are highly effective in damaging in tissue and are considered to be a causative agent for lung cancer in human beings. According to world health organization, radon is first most

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important cause of lung cancer. The motivation of work is to measure radiological health risk level of radon exhalation rates and radium in these areas which would be of great help for radiological database.

Study Area

Sri Ksetra is situated at the present village of Hmawza, 5 miles southeast of modern Pyay, Bago division with location of latitude $18^{\circ} 50' N$ and longitude $95^{\circ} 20' E$. Sri Ksetra is designated as UNESCO World Heritage Sites. The map of Sri Ksetra Ancient City, Pyay Township is shown in Figure 1.

Figure. 1 Map of Sri Ksetra Ancient City, Pyay Township

Materials and Methods

Alpha sensitive LR-115 Type II plastic track detectors commonly known as Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors (SSNTDs) were used to measure the radon concentration. For the measurement of radon concentration and exhalation rates from soil samples, 'CAN' technique has been employed. The areas of the study included are entrance of Hmawzar village, HMA-64(Site Museum), HMA-58(Site Museum), HMA-59 (Site Museum), and near the house which is located at Khin Ba Mound. Soil samples from the surface of the ground, under the depths of 1 ft and 2 ft were taken for each area. The collected soil samples were dried and powdered. Known amount 200 g of each samples were kept inside the plastic can. Alpha sensitive LR-115 Type II plastic track detectors of size (1 cm × 1 cm) were fixed on the bottom of the lid of each can with cello tape such that the sensitive side of the detector faced the samples. The cans were tightly closed from the top and sealed. The geometrical parameters of the container were 8 cm in diameter and 11cm in height. The exposure time of the detector was 100 days. The schematic diagram of the "CAN" technique for measurement of radium and radon exhalation rate of different soil samples is shown in Figure 2.

After exposure time, the detectors were removed and subjected to a chemical etching process in 2.5 N NaOH solutions at $60^{\circ}C$ for one and half hour. After etching, the detectors were washed with water until the surface of the detector became cleaned from etchant. Then, the rinsed detectors were dried with filter paper. Etched tracks show as bright holes in a dark

red background, and are very clearly visible under the optical microscope of magnification 10× - 100×. In this work, track counting was performed by using OLYMPUS BX51 optical microscope with 20× magnification attached with monitor and camera control unit. OLYMPUS BX51 optical microscope is shown in figure 3. Only tracks that have been completely perforated the sensitive layer have been counted. The number of tracks viewed on the monitor were counted view by view changing the vertical and the horizontal position of detector under the microscope. In this work alpha tracks were counted for different ten views. The track density of each sample was calculated by using the track density equation:

$$\text{Track density, } \rho(\text{track/cm}^2) = \frac{\text{Net number of tracks}}{\text{View field of Area}}$$

Radon concentration in the samples was calculated using the following formula: $C_{Rn} = \frac{\rho}{\eta T}$

Where η = the calibration coefficient of LR-115 detector = 0.056 tracks $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}/\text{Bq m}^{-3}$

T = exposure time

Based upon the radon measurement data, exhalation rates were calculated using the following equations: For mass exhalation rate:

$$\text{MER} = \frac{CV\lambda}{M [T + 1/\lambda (e^{-\lambda T} - 1)]}$$

For surface exhalation rate:

$$\text{SER} = \frac{CV\lambda}{A [T + 1/\lambda (e^{-\lambda T} - 1)]}$$

Where C = integrated radon exposure, V = volume of the air in the can, λ = decay constant for radon

Radium concentration in soil has been calculated using the following formula:

$$C_{Ra} = \frac{\rho A h}{K T_e M}$$

Where A = area of the sample

h = distance between the detector and the top of the sample

K = sensitivity factor = 0.0245 tracks $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}/\text{Bq m}^{-3}$

T_e = effective exposure time = $T - \lambda^{-1}(1 - e^{-\lambda T})$

Figure. 2 The schematic diagram of the “CAN” technique for measurement of radon content in different soil samples

Figure. 3 OLYMPUS BX51 optical microscope and alpha tracks on the monitor

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of radium concentration, radon concentration, mass and surface exhalation rates of soil samples of different places are shown in Table 1. For the surface of the ground, radium concentration in soil samples has been found to vary from 0.81 Bqkg^{-1} to 2.59 Bqkg^{-1} . These values of radium concentration are less than the permissible value of 370 Bq kg^{-1} recommended by Organization for Economic Cooperation and Developments, which is acceptable for safe use. The measured values (except A-3, A-5, A-6, A-15) of radon concentration are below the recommended action level. The higher recorded values for radium concentration, surface and mass exhalation rates of the soil from the surface of the ground were found in the location HMA-59. The minimum values of the soil sample were recorded near the house which is located at Khin Ba Mound. The radon exhalation rate in terms of area varies from $105.88 \text{ mBq m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $340.58 \text{ mBq m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ while radon exhalation rate in terms of mass varies from $2.66 \text{ mBq kg}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $8.56 \text{ mBq kg}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$. The radon concentration for the soil which got from the surface of the ground is less than for soil which got from the depth of 1 ft and 2 ft, this means the concentration is increase with increasing in depth.

Figure 4 shows the variation of radium concentration with depth of the soil in different sites of Sri Ksetra Ancient City. The correlation between the radon concentration and radium concentration of soil samples are shown in Figure 5. Figure 6 and 7 represents the surface and mass exhalation rates of radon gas vs radium concentration for different soil samples.

Table. 1 Radon concentration, radium concentration, mass exhalation rate and surface exhalation rate from different soil samples

Sr No.	Sample Code	Radon concentration (Bq m ⁻³)	Radium concentration (Bq kg ⁻¹)	Mass exhalation rate (mBq kg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	Surface exhalation rate (mBq m ⁻² h ⁻¹)
1.	A-1	478.57	2.33	7.71	306.71
2.	A-2	576.21	2.80	9.25	368.05
3.	A-3	653.57	3.18	10.51	418.19
4.	A-4	531.96	2.59	8.56	340.58
5.	A-5	616.78	3.00	9.92	394.72
6.	A-6	666.42	3.24	10.71	426.45
7.	A-7	342.42	1.66	5.51	219.23
8.	A-8	392.12	1.91	6.3	250.96
9.	A-9	469.44	2.28	7.77	300.57
10.	A-10	165.68	0.81	2.66	105.88
11.	A-11	325.85	1.58	5.24	208.56
12.	A-12	428.94	2.09	6.89	274.43
13.	A-13	480.49	2.34	7.73	307.51
14.	A-14	539.40	2.62	8.68	345.38
15.	A-15	622.24	3.03	10.00	398.18

A-1 = the surface of the ground at HMA-58

A-2 = under the depth of 1 ft from the ground at HMA-58

A-3 = under the depth of 2 ft from the ground at HMA-58

A-4 = the surface of the ground at HMA-59

A-5 = under the depth of 1 ft from the ground at HMA-59

A-6 = under the depth of 2 ft from the ground at HMA-59

A-7 = the surface of the ground at HMA-64

A-8 = under the depth of 1 ft from the ground at HMA-64

A-9 = under the depth of 2 ft from the ground at HMA-64

A-10 = the surface of the ground near the house which is located at Khin Ba Mound

- A-11= under the depth of 1 ft from the ground near the house which is located at Khin Ba Mound
- A-12 = under the depth of 2 ft from the ground near the house which is located at Khin Ba Mound
- A-13 = the top layer of the ground entrance of Hmawzar village
- A-14 = under the depth of 1 ft from the ground entrance of Hmawzar village
- A-15 = under the depth of 2 ft from the ground entrance of Hmawzar village

Figure. 4 Variation of radium concentration with depth of the soil in different sites of Sri Ksetra Ancient City

Figure. 5 The correlation between radon concentration and radium concentration of soil samples

Figure. 6 Surface exhalation rate vs radium concentration for soil samples

Figure. 7 Mass exhalation rate vs radium concentration for soil samples

Conclusion

The solid state nuclear track detectors are best suited for the measurement of radium content and radon exhalation rates in soil samples collected from various area of Sri Ksetra Ancient City , Pyay Township. The values of radon exhalation rates obtained are found to be linearly dependence with radium concentration. Moreover, the radon concentration level and radium content increase with the increasing depth of ground. Transport of soil is largely depending on the geology of the area. The observed values of radium concentration in soil samples in the present study are much lower than the recommended permissible value of OECD. The results for the soil sample from the surface of the ground are below the recommended safe limit. Thus, the results reveal that the area is safe for the health hazard effects of radium and radon exhalation are concerned.

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